

Species	RNA Integrity Number*	Number of Replicates: Non-gestation	Number of Replicates: Late-gestation
<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i>	7.25 (6–8.4)	5	5
<i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i>	>8 [†]	3	3
<i>Monodelphis domestica</i>	Unknown [†]	3	3
<i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i>	7.9 (7.5–8.5)	3	5
<i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i>	7.65 (6.8–8.8)	5	5
<i>Pseudemoia entrecasteauxii</i>	>8 [†]	2	3
<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	9.7 (8.3–10)	5	5
<i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	7.05 (6.8–8.1)	2	4

* Median and range of RNA Integrity Numbers are provided for all samples newly extracted for the present study

[†] Samples without precise RIN values were obtained from previous studies (SRA references in main text). We have included values here based on information in those previous studies.